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A SUSTAINABLE APPROACH TO SUGARCANE IRRIGATION: MACHINE LEARNING BASED AUTOMATED SOLAR POWERED WATER PUMPING SYSTEMS AS AN ALTERNATIVE TO DIESEL/KEROSENE PUMPS

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This study presents the development and evaluation of a prototype machine learning based automated solar powered irrigation system as a sustainable alternative to conventional fuel pumps in large scale sugarcane cultivation. The research was conducted over four acres in the dryland area of Pelwatte Sugar Factory, Buttala, Sri Lanka, comparing a 3 HP kerosene pump operated three to four times weekly during dry seasons with a network of four 1 HP solar powered irrigation units. The system aimed to assess environmental performance, water use efficiency, and sustainability as an eco-technology for climate resilient agriculture. The prototype employed an ESP32 microcontroller integrated with a capacitive soil moisture sensor and solar irradiation sensor to monitor soil and sunlight conditions. The ESP32 operated within an analog voltage range of 2.3–2.8 V (12-bit ADC = 2730–3475) under dry soil conditions, with a minimum moisture threshold of 2.2 V (ADC \approx 2854). Sensor data formed the training dataset for an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) model trained to predict irrigation requirements based on real time soil parameters. The trained ANN was connected with the ESP32 and tested through a battery connected solar panel system that automatically activated pumps when soil moisture dropped below the threshold. Performance testing showed each 1 HP solar pump discharged 25–30 L min⁻¹, delivering approximately 9,000–10,800 liters per day per unit over 6–8 hours of sunlight. Moisture recovery time averaged 30–40 minutes, with ANN response within seconds and overall system accuracy of 90%, maintaining soil moisture between 22–28%. Theoretical analyses indicated a 22% improvement in water-use efficiency and a reduction of approximately 285 kg CO₂ per month. The findings confirm that integrating sensing, solar energy, and machine learning provides a scalable, climate smart irrigation solution for sustainable sugarcane cultivation in Sri Lanka's dry zones.

Keywords: Irrigation, Sugarcane cultivation, Solar Powered water pump, Automation system, Sustainability